

METHODOLOGY FOR PREPARING THE FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHER TO FORM A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE BASED ON SPORTS GAMES

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Abstract: This article reveals the role of sports games in maintaining the health of a future primary school teacher, proposes a model of preparing him for the formation of a healthy lifestyle of primary school students through physical education, which is implemented principles and stages of improvement, pedagogical conditions of effectiveness are given.

Key words: health, healthy lifestyle, model, formation, training, teacher, school student, physical education, methodology, model.

Introduction.

Currently, higher pedagogical education is faced with the task of not only performing professional activities in a high-quality manner, but also preparing students for maintaining health and forming a healthy lifestyle. This is especially true for primary education teachers who are involved in educating young people in all aspects of their lives, including shaping their healthy lifestyle. Taking into account the most important role of physical activity in maintaining health, the necessary professional quality of a teacher of primary education becomes his readiness to use physical education tools for these purposes. An important condition for the effectiveness of the educational process is the personal example of a teacher who leads a healthy lifestyle free from bad habits of physical education and sports. The relevance of this scientific research is the need to prepare primary school teachers for practical activities on the formation of a healthy lifestyle in future primary school teachers through physical education and the lack of a scientifically based program for its implementation. related to the conflict between The task was to develop a teaching model for the formation of a healthy lifestyle of future primary education teachers through physical education and to check its effectiveness. According to the proposed model, the educational process is based on the following didactic principles:

- ❖ dynamism that ensures continuous, progressive improvement and correction of the knowledge system on health care and healthy lifestyle formation of future primary education teachers with the help of physical education tools;
- ❖ scientific, which includes relying on the generalized strict scientific theoretical knowledge in the field of human health care, as well as the organization and implementation of physical education and wellness activities;
- ❖ students transfer new information received through their personal experience and knowledge, turn it into updated knowledge in the process of activity, and then use it on the basis of sports games for the healthy life of future primary education teachers continuity consisting of their use to form a style;

- ❖ continuity that contributes to the creation of a coherent connection between the goal, content and activity in the process of preparing students for the formation of a healthy lifestyle and effectively achieving the goal;
- ❖ variability that gives the opportunity to choose different options for solving a specific problem and use the most effective methods of activity;
- ❖ complexity manifested in the use of systems and elements included in the developed model, which includes all directions of activity, various forms and methods of preparing students for the formation of a healthy lifestyle, expediency, integrity in preparing for the formation of a healthy lifestyle, didactic principles of availability and consistency of knowledge play an important role.

Based on the model we have developed, the effectiveness of this process is ensured by the interrelated and interrelated components of its components. The motivational component is aimed at forming the attitude of students towards education of health and a healthy lifestyle, as well as creating the foundation of necessary theoretical knowledge, healthy lifestyle of future primary education teachers through sports games, aimed at mastering the main concepts, ideas and facts that confirm the importance of the formation of the style.

The cognitive component shows the theoretical readiness of the student to maintain health and to form a healthy lifestyle of schoolchildren through sports games, to develop new knowledge about the essence, structure, functions and tasks of physical education activities. The component of the model based on the curriculum is the importance of acquired skills and abilities for the formation of educational goals and a healthy lifestyle of students through physical education, as well as methods and methods of independent activity, the ability to act in this activity, it involves knowing the implementation characteristics.

Taking into account that the model curriculum of the state educational institution for physical education does not sufficiently cover the issues of healthy lifestyle and its formation in students, we introduce to it the concepts of health, healthy lifestyle, its components, age We introduced a number of theoretical topics related to the formation of a healthy lifestyle in students, physical education, the impact of these tools on the development of children. The activity component provides the future teacher with practical skills and abilities to develop, organize and conduct activities related to the formation of a healthy lifestyle of elementary school students through physical education. allows to provide, to develop the readiness of students to promote health and healthy lifestyle, to put knowledge, skills and abilities into practice and to develop a personal Model for health activities in physical education model curriculum of physical education and sports activities, organization of holidays, mastering the methods of controlling and monitoring the functional state of the body of primary school students during physical education classes, reproducing the pedagogical conditions of the real educational process at school It was supplemented with methodological and practical exercises on solving educational and modeling problems. The reflective component reflects the integrated assessment of the results of preparing students for the formation of a healthy lifestyle and includes the student's reflection on himself, health, self-analysis and his own knowledge, skills, It is manifested in the correction of skills and the ability to self-manage activities. In the preparation of the student, his interaction with the teacher plays an important role, which we consider on the basis of subject-subject relations. Such a process is characterized by subjectivity, freedom of communication, dialogization, self-development. A

student does not become a subject in the learning process, but he is initially a carrier of subjective experience.

The interaction of the subjects of the pedagogical process includes a certain pedagogical skill of the teacher and the level of cognitive abilities and readiness of the student to form a healthy lifestyle of young students. Successful implementation of the proposed model largely depends on compliance with a number of pedagogical conditions. Person-oriented education allows creating a favorable environment for the personal growth of the student; methodological direction in physical education and wellness activities provides processes of understanding and development of individuality of students. Humanization of education is aimed at the formation of health and a healthy lifestyle, the development of moral qualities that show an active attitude towards society, work and its results, other people and oneself. The interdisciplinary integration of preparing students for the formation of a healthy lifestyle of young students through physical education includes knowledge of the theoretical foundations and multifaceted interdisciplinary relations of such disciplines as anatomy, physiology, hygiene, youth psychology, etc. during the research, the main criteria of the elementary school teacher's readiness to form a healthy lifestyle of schoolchildren through physical education were determined:

- ❖ formation of skills and abilities - students' knowledge of the characteristics of primary school students;
- ❖ availability of skills and abilities to form a healthy lifestyle through physical education; the ability to plan and organize motor activities taking into account the sex, age and individual characteristics of children;
- ❖ personal motivational attention to a healthy lifestyle - the student has a positive motivation to form and maintain his own healthy lifestyle, as well as to use knowledge, skills and abilities in future professional activities;
- ❖ development of internal motivation - formation of a healthy lifestyle of schoolchildren through physical education, positive personal self-awareness and superiority of motives and aspirations for professional direction, vision obtained for the realization of professional potential the use of skills and abilities, as well as self-awareness of the individual.

During the testing of the model, four levels of students' readiness to form a healthy lifestyle of schoolchildren through physical education were determined.

Unstable attitude to adaptive physical education and wellness activities, initial concepts of health and healthy lifestyle, lack of in-depth theoretical and practical knowledge, skills and abilities on the use of physical education tools in its formation is described.

It is characterized by a stable attitude towards reproductive and physical education and wellness activities, the manifestation of interest in working with children, the ability to use standard recommendations, efforts to form a healthy lifestyle of schoolchildren, and physical education tools.

The effective level is characterized by the student's desire to learn the features of forming a healthy lifestyle of young students through physical education. In the process of acquiring knowledge, he subjectively receives new information and assimilates it in the process of independent work on the indicative basis of exemplary action, but using new actions and knowledge. Creative level, high motivation to form a healthy lifestyle with a clear cognitive and professional character, firm belief in its necessity and practical application in

the future, ability to carry out research, self-reflection by analyzing one's own activities It is characterized by high reflectivity associated with zi organization. The program for preparing a future teacher for the formation of a healthy lifestyle of schoolchildren includes three stages (*diagnosis, formation and evaluation of effectiveness*), each of them has its own goals, tasks, forms of organization, their solutions has the means and methods of doing and is aimed at a certain result.

During the practical training, the skills and abilities necessary for the organization of various physical education and wellness activities, as well as for monitoring the functional condition of the students, were mastered. In all classes, there was a free exchange of ideas among students on the topics of educational materials. This form of transfer made it possible not only to activate the students' cognitive activity, but also to direct the group's opinion to a positive assessment of the discussed problem, and then use it to change negative attitudes and misconceptions. Group work and business games simulating the conditions of professional pedagogical activity allowed students to creatively approach problem solving based on the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities on the studied topic. The research work of the students helped to develop modern pedagogical thinking and further improve the future elementary school teacher. Evaluation of the work performed by students was carried out by the teacher, other students and the performer himself. During such a difficult time, it allowed students who have work to see themselves from the outside, to further develop, strengthen and improve the system of knowledge, skills and qualifications, to use them in real conditions of educational and professional activities, in non-standard situations, creative pedagogical activity helped to acquire experience, to join scientific-research works. In order to evaluate the effectiveness of preparing students for the formation of a healthy lifestyle of young students through physical culture, their level of readiness was compared at the initial stage of the experiment and at the end of it.

Conclusion:

Evaluating the dynamics of students' willingness to form a healthy lifestyle in general (*by summing up the scores of individual components*), it can be noted that positive changes in all indicators were noted in the experimental group, while in the control group they did not change significantly. . Thus, the results of the experimental work show the effectiveness of the developed model of preparing the elementary school teacher for the formation of a healthy lifestyle of elementary school students through physical education, which is a recommendation for introducing them into the educational process of pedagogical universities.

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